

AN ATTEMPT TO UNDERSTAND ROOT CAUSE BEHIND HIGH LEVELS OF LEAD CONTENT IN “MAGGI”

Sudha Shrivastava, Sarita Yadav
Govt. Kalidas Girl’s College, Ujjain (M.P.)

Maggi Noodles by Nestle are banned and taken off shelves in India because of the high lead levels in the product. In my opinion, Nestle is not deliberately increasing the lead content, but lead content can be found in greater than expected quantity due to increase in lead content in its raw materials.

One may read all the ingredients of the Maggi noodles as we as its taste enhancer mentioned on the wrapper of the product.

What can be the cause of presence of lead, what can be its source and how does it affect human health?

Lead is present in all sections of our environment. Air, Soil, Water, every element of environment contains lead. Lead and lead compounds have been used under wide variety of products found in and around our houses, and now as per reports, even the most handy food product called Maggi noodles has lead, more than acceptable to human health. As we are aware, lead is a naturally occurring element found in small amount in the earth’s crust. While it has some beneficial uses, it can be toxic to human and animals causing health issues.

Lead may not be present in the noodles as such, but in my opinion, it may be present in the taste maker. If we go through the content of taste makers, we can find that all the ingredients are naturally grown, then how can lead be present in excessive amount in its taste enhancer. It can be possible. Due to the increasing pollution of our land, water and air. Wide range of effluents are

drained out in river and other water bodies unchecked, are highly toxic, with lead being a significant part of the toxicity. Through water, lead flows into soil and land under cultivation. Unfortunately, Lead does not naturally breakdown and decomposed. Instead it gets accumulated and with each passing step in the food chain, its concentration becomes higher and higher.

A further test conducted by a laboratory in Kolkata, has confirmed not only the presence of high levels of lead but also its high levels of monosodium glutamate, a taste enhancer. We can eat minerals up to a permissible limit because minerals upto a certain amount is necessary for the functioning of body, but a large amount of lead has some drastic effects on our body.

Since maggi noodles have been accepted by all the sections of the society: children, adults and senior citizens, and ingested lead can reach out to all parts of our body such as brain, nervous system, kidney, liver, bones and blood. It can even decay teeth if it gets deposited.

Lead is particularly dangerous to children because their growing bodies have more tendency to absorb lead than adults do and their brain and nervous systems are more sensitive to damaging effects of lead.

Even low levels of lead among children may result in

- Behavior and learning problems
- Lower IQ and hyperactivity
- Slower growth
- Hearing problems
- Anemia

In rare cases, ingestion of lead can even cause coma and ultimately death.

The purpose behind writing this paper is to attempt to bring attention of our society towards increased lead content, not just in Maggi but also towards the elements of environment and take necessary steps to minimize its accumulation among irrigated fields, agricultural land, water bodies and other elements of the food productions.

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